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Protection of genomic data and the Australian *Privacy Act*: when is genomic data ‘personal information’?

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What is the issue?

3.3.2 Is Genomic Information ‘Personal Information’ under Privacy Laws?

Genomic information will typically only fall within scope of privacy laws if it meets the legislative definition of personal information.

It can be difficult for those processing genomic information to confidently assess when it is reasonably identifiable; this is particularly the case as data moves between different collections with different permutations of possible (future) data linkage.

https://www.utas.edu.au/_data/assets/pdf_file/0005/1576940/Essentially-Ours-CLG-OP11-1.pdf

What do we mean by ‘genetic information’?

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Scientific
definition

Legal
definition

When is genomic data personal information?

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Genomic
Data

Genomic data includes

- ‘raw’ sequence read data – including whole genome and exome sequence and single nucleotide variants, and
- ‘analysed data’ which identifies differences between sequence data and a reference genome: often written to a variant call format (VCF) which can include particular variant identifiers.

This may be annotated and include supporting data (which may relate to significance of variants) and/or supplementary biographical or clinical data.

What do we mean by ‘personal information’?

In the *Privacy Act 1988* (Cth)
personal information means

**“information or an opinion
about an identified individual,
or an individual who is
reasonably identifiable:**

- (a) whether the information or opinion is true or not; and
- (b) whether the information or opinion is recorded in a material form or not.”

What do we mean by ‘genetic information’?

Sensitive information includes (S6(1)):

(b) health information about an individual [defined in S6FA]

“genetic information about an individual in a form that is, or could be, predictive of the health of the individual or a genetic relative of the individual” (S6FA(d)), and

(c) **genetic information that is not health information**

When is genomic data, personal information??

Documents and records containing no obvious identifying features may nevertheless ‘take on the quality’ of identifiability through the context in which they are held (See e.g. *WL v Randwick City Council (GD)* [2007] NSWADTAP 58 [15].)

In *Privacy Commissioner v Telstra Corporation Ltd* Kenny and Edelman JJ wrote that ‘**a determination of whether the identity can reasonably be ascertained will require an evaluative conclusion**’ [2017] FCAFC 4 (*Telstra*).

OAIC Guidance – reasonable identifiability requires contextual consideration:

- a. **The nature and amount of information**
- b. **Who will hold and have access to the information**
- c. **The other information that is available, and the practicability of using that information to identify an individual**

When is genomic data, personal information??

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Applying the test to genomic data: volume, richness, uniqueness

Different types of genomic data (eg raw data or interpreted or annotated data) vary according to volume, richness and uniqueness

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Some information is unique to a particular person, and may in itself identify that person

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Significance of such features (including uniqueness) must be interpreted *in context*

Where it is technically possible to identify an individual by referencing it against other available information, entities should also consider the likelihood that this would occur.

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Data environment or “data situation” considers all material factors e.g. who has access (open cf restricted), what other information is available to them, time, cost and resource

Technical, organisational and legal methods to affect data situation

The evaluative process of assessing identifiability is dynamic and ongoing – not ‘set and forget’

Fluid and dynamic interpretive contexts

‘[t]he same information may be personal information in one situation, but de-identified information in another’

Australian Government, Office of the Australian Information Commissioner, *De-identification and the Privacy Act* (March 2018), 14.

‘[i]nformation holdings can ... be dynamic, and the character of information can change over time’, so that determinations of identifiability with regard to the same data may change with new developments and changing environment.

Australian Government, Office of the Australian Information Commissioner, *What is Personal Information?* (May 2017), 6, 10.

Conclusion

Genomic data and Genetic information are overlapping concepts, with overlap dependent on evaluative conclusion in all the circumstances

Identifiability depends on data (volume, richness, uniqueness) + context = data situation

Control over context is key – dependent on organizational, technical and contractual controls

Data situation may be dynamic – so assessment should consider fluidity of interpretive context

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Genomic data and Genetic information are overlapping concepts, with overlap dependent on evaluative conclusion in all the circumstances

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Data situation may be dynamic – so assessment should consider fluidity of interpretive context

Implications for –

- Understanding rights and responsibilities under the *Privacy Act 1988 (Cth)*
- Critical evaluation

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Thank you

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